

Ungrading: Using Feedback and Reflection to Address Equity Challenges in Large Classes

Heather Bennett <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3918-2817>

Bridget Curren <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6759-2526>

Office of Digital Learning, Innovation, and Strategy, SUNY Empire State University,
Saratoga Springs, NY, U.S.A

Abstract

This paper provides an overview of ungrading, the practice of removing traditional grades from assessments to prioritize students' processes and improvement and explores ungrading as a strategy to increase equity. We discuss how ungrading was implemented in the specific case of an undergraduate general education history course in Singapore in Spring 2019; the course included 120 students across three course sections. While a final grade was required by the program, all assessments within the course were ungraded.

Through this example, we highlight effective practices, especially the use of reflective essays. We explore how these essays enabled collaborative grading, in which learners and instructor both contributed to the assignment of a final grade. We address how this afforded opportunities to apply equitable practices, including opportunities to affirm students' diverse identities and individualize learning paths, despite the size of the class. Finally, we discuss additional implications for ungrading in large courses, including the use of collaborative grading in STEM settings, persistent inequities, and the impact of ungrading on instructors' workload.

Keywords: *Ungrading; Undergraduate education; Teaching and learning; Large classes*

1. Introduction

Ungrading addresses two common issues related to equity in large classes: the challenge of fostering a sense of belonging and the difficulty of individualizing learning pathways. As such, ungrading can be a powerful tool for increasing equity in large classes. In the following sections, we define ungrading and examine the intersections of research around ungrading, equity, and large classes. We then detail a specific example of ungrading in a large class facilitated by one of the paper's authors in spring 2019 in Singapore, including the instructor's rationale for implementing ungrading. In our analysis of students' work in the course, we reflect on how ungrading created opportunities to affirm students' diverse identities and customize learning paths, thereby enabling a greater sense of belonging and creating equitable opportunities to thrive within the course structure. In closing, we briefly consider additional implications for STEM, equity, and workload when implementing ungrading.

2. Literature Review

2.1. What is Ungrading?

The word "ungrading" means raising an eyebrow at grades as a systemic practice, distinct from simply "not grading" (Stommel, 2023)

Ungrading, sometimes called "de-grading" or "going gradeless," is the practice of removing numeric and letter grades from some or all assessments for students' learning and instead focusing on feedback, iteration, and improvement of learners' skills. This can take the shape of removing grades from some assignments or eliminating grades from a course altogether (though a final grade usually is still required by an institution or program) (Elbow, 1997; Stommel, 2023). There are also multiple frameworks for ungrading, including contract grading, labor-based grading, and collaborative grading.

Contract grading involves a negotiated agreement between an instructor and student stating what tasks a learner needs to complete and to what standards in order to achieve the grade the student is aiming to earn (Litterio, 2018). Labor-based grading is similarly negotiated, but places greater emphasis on time and work and minimizes the impact of some traditional assessment standards, especially quality of writing standards (Inoue, 2023). Collaborative grading, in which learners and instructor determined final grades together based on students' perception of their achievements and the instructor's observations of their growth throughout the course, was the foundation for the example detailed below (Whysel, 2022).

2.2. Ungrading in Higher Education

Ungrading has received significant attention as an alternative approach to traditional harsh numeric grading practices. It demonstrates potential to be a student-centered approach positioned to combat issues of equity, learning gaps, accessibility, self-efficacy, and student autonomy (Stommel, 2018; Blum, 2017). A study of Undergraduate Library and Information Science students revealed that ungrading enhanced the learning environment, making it more inclusive and encouraging students to take responsibility over their own learning outcomes (Rapchak et al., 2023). Another study revealed similar results: ungrading utilized in an upper-level computer science course increased student learning motivation, autonomy, and self-efficacy. The same study revealed decreases in stress and anxiety with ungrading in place (Spurlock, 2023).

2.3. Ungrading, Equity, and Large Classes

Research shows that harsh grading practices can further the learning gap in already marginalized groups (Ko, 2021). For example, the utilization of harsh grading practices in large enrollment introductory level foundation or prerequisite courses, known as “weed out courses”, has been demonstrated to significantly impact student success. In one study, STEM students receiving D, F, or W grades in these “weed out courses” were at risk for not returning to their institution for the following year. The same study demonstrated that students with otherwise good GPAs elected to switch out of their STEM major if they performed poorly in a “weed-out course” their first two years of college (Weston et al., 2019).

High enrollment can be a limiting factor in the feedback and time intensive approaches of ungrading. However, preliminary evidence in a large, freshman software engineering course and in general education college physics course reveals promise. In a two-year case study of utilizing ungrading in a large enrollment, higher education software engineering program, the instructor utilized the collaborative feedback model of ungrading to address systemic issues of equity. In her study, she found that the quality of group final projects submitted increased with each iteration of ungrading for that given semester. The same study also found an increase in positive classroom culture, a shift to self-improvement over points, and a re-valuing of the intrinsic curiosity that leads to deeper learning (Brewer, 2024).

Furthermore, a recent study investigated the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for ungrading in a general education college Physics course to address equity issues and lack of diversity in assessment strategies. The study found that, in conjunction with the vast capabilities of generative AI, creating diversified assessments lead to an emphasis on students’ individual areas of growth. The same study found that using AI to generate personal learning plans resulted in a real-time focus on student individual progress as well as a deviation from vague, blanket formative assessment tools (Crogman et al., 2023). Johanna Brewer, professor of software engineering and author of the case study cited above states the following in reference to the conclusion of her work with ungrading:

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“By eliminating exams, rarefying rubrics, and prioritizing collaborative work products, it is possible to rewild computer science classrooms to become more inclusive spaces for exploration. (2024, p15)

2.4. Problems with Ungrading

Ungrading is not a cure-all for inequitable education. In some cases, ungrading may actually widen equity gaps by removing an important piece of structure from the course (Supiano, 2022). Craig (2021) notes that contract grading in a single class does little to address systemic racism in higher education or bolster success for BIPOC (Black, Indigenous, Person of Color) students. Likewise, Dyer (2024) critiques the outsized impact of implicit biases in ungraded courses; instructor’s evaluations of student’s work and student’s assessment of their own work is inherently biased and therefore cannot decrease inequity. Craig and Dyer agree that traditional grades are inequitable and that alternatives are necessary to increase equitable grading in which all students receive the appropriate grade for their work, regardless of identity. However, they do not see ungrading as a viable solution to problems of inequity.

3. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

3.1. University at Buffalo, Singapore Institute of Management (Spring 2019)

The example of ungrading detailed in this paper took place in spring 2019 in a World Civilizations I course consisting of 120 students across three sections of the course. The course was conducted as part of the University at Buffalo, Singapore Institute of Management undergraduate program (UB-SIM program) and included students at all stages of their degrees. The UB-SIM program is a private education option, hosted in space rented from SIM, for Singaporean and other Southeast Asian students and as of Spring 2019 it served around 1500 students. The program offers a small number of majors: Business, Communications, Economics, International Trade, Psychology, and Sociology. Upon completion of their degree, students receive a University at Buffalo degree just as if they had attended the university in Buffalo, NY, but without the added expense of years studying abroad.

In keeping with University at Buffalo’s liberal arts tradition, students are required to take general education courses to complete their degrees. The example course detailed below, World Civilizations I (encompassing the period from 3500 BCE to 1500 CE), was one option to fulfil the history/sociology general education credit. The instructor was experienced, having taught the course from Fall 2014 to Spring 2019. As the UB-SIM program did not offer a history major, the course syllabus was subject to approval by the program directors but did not need to adhere to departmental. This left the instructor free to experiment with alternative assessment methods.

3.2. Why Ungrading?

In Spring 2019, the instructor chose to experiment with ungrading through the use of a collaborative grading framework. The choice was partly an extension of the instructor's previous teaching practices. In earlier instances of the course, the instructor implemented practices shared in common with collaborative ungrading, including co-creating syllabi and rubrics with students, facilitating process-oriented projects that weighed growth alongside the final output, and inviting metacognitive reflection about the ways course material intersected with students' experiences. Eliminating all but the final grade from the course was an organic next step.

The instructor was also seeking a way to reduce grading time in a large course. In spring 2019, the class consisted of 120 students, distributed across three sections. Enrolments in previous terms ranged from 130 to 195 students. Her hope was to eliminate the "data entry" portion of assessment and instead focus on conversations with students and robust feedback (Burnett, n.d.). Ideally, this would result in both less time grading and a more satisfying assessment experience for everyone. As noted in the reflections below, only the latter was ultimately true.

3.3. Introducing Ungrading in the Course

During the first class, the instructor presented the syllabus to students and asked them to review the document in small groups then post questions about the course in a Google Slides Q&A. The syllabus included a list of the assessments for the course (attendance, participation, pre-class responses, engagement and learning essays, scaffolded stages of a final group project) followed by details about ungrading in the course.

The instructor explained the course would employ a collaborative ungrading framework in which both students' assessment of their work and instructor observations would determine final grades in the course. Two Learning and Engagement Essays, submitted by students at the middle and end of term, served as the mechanism for collaborative ungrading. In these essays, the instructor tasked students to suggest their own grade and support this suggestion by reflecting on their learning and participation in the course. In 1000-1200 words, students would answer the following questions:

1. What have you learned in the course? (This could include details about content knowledge, acquired skills, or new outlooks).
2. How have you engaged with the class content, activities, and/or your peers and prof?
3. Are there any ways you would like to improve your learning or engagement going forward?
4. If you had to choose your grade for the course now, what would it be?

The instructor requested that learners include a title, introduction, thesis statement, conclusion, and best effort at accurate grammar and spelling. Students also needed to include

references to course content, evidence of self-awareness and reflection, and an honest assessment of what they were doing well and what still needed work. Finally, the explanation included reminders that the assignment was not graded and therefore creativity (for example, including GIFs or submitting a video essay) was encouraged.

The instructor reserved the right to adjust the final grade suggested in an essay in three instances: if a student suggested a grade that was lower than their work merited (as observed by the instructor), if a student did not consistently attend class and/or did not complete a significant portion of the assigned work, or if a student failed to correct issues related to academic honesty.

4. Reflections

Equity was not one of the instructor's original goals for ungrading and, as noted above, ungrading alone cannot reduce inequality in education. However, the framework as implemented in the World Civilizations course did create opportunities to affirm students' diverse identities and individualize students' learning paths. The Learning and Engagement Essays submitted by students demonstrated the extent to which ungrading successfully achieved these goals in the World Civilizations course.

4.1. Affirming Students' Diverse Identities

Carey Borkoski (2020) writes of belonging:

When there is belonging, the individuals in the community believe and trust that they are valued as people within the community. This is not about assimilation or congruence. Instead, it's about creating feelings of social connectedness, support, and respect.

She notes the myriad benefits of a strong sense of belonging, including increased student motivation, improved relationships among instructors and students, higher GPAs, and higher rates of persistence, retention, and graduation (Borkoski, 2020).

Affirming students' identities and perspectives is a key piece of fostering belonging. Reflecting on class conversations about the history of Christianity in the Roman Empire, a student shared their perspective, "I feel that the more educated I get, the more sceptical I get regarding this 'faith'" but then qualified, "I'm not disagreeing with Christianity." Another student noted regarding a class on Judaism, "Learning this topic was hard due to my religion bias-ness but I do agree with the class takeaway on how belief and action are central to my identity." The students initially were apologetic about their perspectives, which afforded the instructor an opportunity to affirm the learners' perspectives. In the essay feedback, she noted that students' disagreement was welcome in the course and did not prevent them from effectively understanding and analyzing the content.

4.2. Individualized Student Learning Paths

Blum (2017) notes the effectiveness of students developing individual plans for demonstrating learning and engaging in self-evaluation. These practices proved similarly effective in the World Civilizations course. Collaborative ungrading allowed students to create their own path to demonstrating learning, draw the instructor's attention to students' strengths, and celebrate their growth during the course.

For example, many students wrote that they did not feel comfortable speaking in front of the whole class (a traditional marker of participation) and instead chose to participate in other ways:

I feel more comfortable speaking up and expressing my ideas through the small groups in class discussions. On top of that, I find myself questioning more about what we learn in a class like the time I approached you to ask about the fall of the Ancient Egyptian Empire.

Students also frequently highlighted engagement practices the instructor could not have observed otherwise, including contributions to small group discussions, a specific point they were proud of in an assignment, or some external research they completed after an idea in class piqued their curiosity. One student explicitly connected the size of the course and the benefit of having a space to detail areas for growth:

The class is quite big, so I'm not sure if you already noticed this, but I have not been putting my best effort into preparing for class.

In their second essays, students also drew attention to how they had improved throughout the course, often referencing feedback the instructor provided in the first essay:

I mentioned in my previous Engagement & Learning Essay that I found myself succumbing to technological usage but I have learnt to put my phone either in my bag or under the table since, because "Out of sight, out of mind" right?

The second learning essays afforded students a space to celebrate their improvements and provided opportunities for the instructor to affirm and encourage their continued growth.

4.3. Ongoing Challenges for Equity and Workload

In the UB-SIM program, student qualitative data revealed that ungrading enhanced student personal identities and enriched their individual learning paths for a large class of general education humanities students. Students in this iteration of collaborative ungrading demonstrated increased personal growth, improved metacognitive strategies, and were able to adopt the role of an active facilitator in their own learning process. As demonstrated in the literature review, ungrading can also be applied in a STEM setting with similar positive effects on student engagement, growth, and autonomy.

Nonetheless, elements of inequity persisted. The instructor found she needed to increase female student's grades more frequently than male students and, like Dyer (2024), noticed male students were more likely to challenge instructor feedback or the final grade than other students. Looking back, the instructor also wonders in how many cases the final grade was influenced by implicit bias. For example, did students who attended class less frequently receive equitable feedback and final grades?

Finally, given the focus of this paper on large classes, it is worth noting that ungrading did not significantly reduce instructor grading (or assessment) time in the example detailed above. The size of the class proved too great an obstacle. However, the course instructor found that she was able to eliminate some of the more tedious aspects of grading (such as attendance tracking or discussion grading). It is possible that the use of AI, as noted in the literature review, will help further reduce grading time while still enabling individualization of feedback in future courses.

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